

Microscopic Structure and Intramural Ganglion of Urinary Bladder of Cat

P. Jagapathi Ramayya, A. Prasanth Babu, H.S. Patki and T.S. Chandrasekhara Rao

Department of Veterinary Anatomy and Histology, College of Veterinary Science, Sri Venkateswara Veterinary University, Tirupathi 517 502, Andhra Pradesh

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The presence of autonomic ganglia is generally noted at the base of the urinary bladder and in the vicinity of the ureterovesical junction (Schulman, 1972) in human. Banks (1981) Trautmann and Fiebiger (1957) reported parasympathetic ganglia in urinary bladder and domestic animals. However, in domestic cat no information is available on the same, hence the present study was envisaged.

Materials and Methods

Six adult cats irrespective of the sex and age, which were brought for postmortem examination, were utilized for the present study. Urinary bladders were collected immediately after death. Tissue pieces were taken from body, neck and ureterovesical junction of urinary bladder. These tissue samples were preserved in 10% Neutral buffered formalin and were processed for paraffin sections of 5-6 micron thickness. The sections were subjected to Haematoxylin and Eosin staining method for general histomorphology (Singh and Sulochana, 1997).

Results and Discussion

Urinary bladder of cat was divisible into vertex, body and a neck. The wall of the urinary bladder consisted of distinct mucosa, *tunica muscularis* and *tunica serosa*. In the present study, the mucosa was observed to be highly folded and it was lined by transitional type of epithelium. *Lamina muscularis* was absent. Thus *lamina*

propria blended with submucosa. Similarly, Dellmann (1993) noted the absence of *lamina muscularis* in the urinary bladder of cat, but it was distinct in other domestic animals.

The *tunica muscularis* of urinary bladder of cat consisted of three layers viz., inner, middle and outer layers. The muscle fibre bundles in the outer and the inner layers were oriented in longitudinal direction. The outermost layer was observed as a thin layer, whereas, the middle layer was the thickest of all. Further, the muscle bundles of the middle layer were chiefly circular or oblique in orientation. Each muscle fibre bundle was comprised of tightly packed smooth muscle cells with narrow connective tissue spaces between them.

In the present investigation, intramural ganglion cells were noted in the muscular coat of urinary bladder. Dixon *et al.* (1983) described that these intramural neurons presumably corresponded to the acetylcholinesterase positive ganglion cells.

In cat urinary bladder intramural ganglionic neurons were closely placed and had intimate association with each other. Further, many satellite cells surrounded the neurons peripherally. The close apposition of some intramural neurons in the wall of the bladder raises the possibility of cell to cell interaction without the involvement of neurotransmitter substance (Gilpin *et al.* 1983). These intramural

*Corresponding author : Email : drjagapathi_palla@yahoo.com

Fig 1. Photomicrograph of urinary bladder of cat showing propria submucosa (SM), Tunica muscularis (M) and Parasympathetic ganglion (G).

ganglions were enclosed by a connective tissue capsule. The intramural glanglionic neurons were parasympathetic in type. In the muscular coat of urinary bladder several nerve terminals were also observed close to the ganglions.

Summary

Urinary bladder of cat was divisible into vertex, body and a neck. The wall of the urinary bladder

consisted of distinct mucosa, *tunica muscularis* and *tunica serosa*. The muscular tunic of urinary bladder of cat consisted of three layers viz., inner, middle and outer layers. Intramural ganglion cells were noted in the muscular coat of urinary bladder in cat. The glanglionic neurons were parasympathetic type.

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Phone : 0141-2760672, Mobile : 09413341683, Email : drsharmars@gmail.com